

INVESTIGATION OF DYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES USING VIBRATING BEAM TECHNIQUE

Ferhat KADIOGLU¹, Aysun DOGANGUN² and Tufan SEZENOZ²

¹*Ataturk University, Mechanical Engineering Department, 25240 Erzurum, Turkey*

²*Turkish Aerospace Industries, Design & Development Department, Kavaklıdere, Ankara, Turkey*

ABSTRACT: The aim of this paper is to investigate dynamic properties of composites by using vibrating beam technique. The composite specimens with free-free end conditions were vibrated at their fundamental nodes. An electro-magnetic shaker was used to vibrate the specimens and the response of them was taken by means of a microphone. It has been shown that this technique produces accurate and repeatable results and that the specimens having high values of stiffness give low damping values. Fibre orientations have important effects on the dynamic properties of composites.

KEYWORDS: damping, flexural modulus, vibrating beam, free-free ends

INTRODUCTION

A quasi-static test is usually employed to test materials to failure in order to obtain the full record of stress-strain behaviour. The test is useful especially for high stress and strain levels. However, as far as the elastic limit of materials is concerned, a dynamic test in vibration is preferred since it is much more practical and accurate, especially under different environmental conditions. If a wide range of temperature, say from -150 to $+150$ C, is considered, with a good test set-up preparation, the elastic properties of a material can be found from only one specimen simple and cheap [1]. For example, the error of dynamic measurement of moduli is of the order of 0.1%, whereas static measurement cannot be better than 5% [2]. Another important data that can be found through the resonant vibration technique is the damping property of a material.

Accordingly, when the dynamic properties of a material in vibration are considered, the modulus (stiffness) and damping are emphasised. These two values are desired to be high since the former introduces a load-bearing feature into structural systems, while the latter provides energy dissipation under resonant vibration and noise. Unfortunately, it is very difficult to obtain the two in a desirable amount in an isotropic material as high damping

materials usually imply low stiffness and strength. In order to combine the two benefits, engineers or designers have developed composites, which can be produced from two or more different materials.

Fibre-reinforced polymers consisting of two components, the fibre and the matrix, bonded together. These are used increasingly for some applications where high strength and damping but light mass are required, such as in the aerospace and automobile industry. The stiffness of the material is controlled by the fibres, whilst the softer matrix provides support for the fibres and a path for load transfer and, most importantly, a medium for energy dissipation. The amount of the stiffness and damping depends on the manner in which the fibres and matrix are combined in polymer composites, varying from unidirectional, continuous fibre reinforcement, and laminates consisting of oriented layers of unidirectional plies, to randomly oriented chopped fibre reinforcement. The dynamic properties of a composite are measured with respect to fibre orientation in three basic modes of deformation: in tension parallel to the fibre, in tension transverse to the fibres and in longitudinal shear [3]

The aim this paper is to investigate dynamic properties of composites using vibrating beam technique, with free-free beam end conditions. Three different specimen types were tested, among which two were carbon fibre reinforced polymer having the same matrix but different fibre orientations and the other was glass fibre reinforced polymer.

THEORY

Damping Measurements

Damping is defined in a number of different way yet related ways. Those commonly used are summarised by Singh [3] and as follows;

a-) The quality factor, Q

This is determined from the curve of displacement amplitude against frequency, obtained when the amplitude of the exciting force is kept constant (shown in Figure 1). The 'half-power bandwidth' is (f_2-f_1) where f_2, f_1 are the frequencies at which the displacement falls to

$1/\sqrt{2}$ of its maximum value, reached at f_n , the resonant frequency. The quality factor, Q , is given by:

$$Q = \frac{f_n}{f_2 - f_1} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Definition of damping for quality factor, Q .

b-) The Loss Factor, η

This is defined as:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\Delta W}{W} \quad (2)$$

where ΔW and W are the energy dissipated and the maximum stored energy, respectively.

Graessner and Wong [4] give a description of how these entities describing damping are related. The relationship is as follows, for small damping:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{Q}$$

(3)

Flexural Modulus Measurements

The natural frequency of a beam, f_n , is found as:

$$f_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\lambda_n}{l} \right)^2 \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho t b}} \quad (4)$$

where $\lambda_n = 4.730041$ is the 1st eigenvalue for free-free end conditions,

n is the mode number,

E is the flexural modulus,

I is the second moment of area,

l is the length,

ρ is the mass density,

t is the thickness, and

b is the width of the beam.

EXPERIMENTAL

The specimens

Before the dynamic measurements of the specimens, a digital micrometer was used measuring at several positions in the length, thickness and width of them to be used in the calculations and taking the average of them. Electronic scales were used to weigh the beams so that density of each beam could be obtained. The actual measurements of the specimens used are shown in Table 1.

Three different specimen types were tested, among which the two were carbon fibre reinforced polymer (epoxy) having the same polymer matrix but different fibre orientations.

These composites are produced by Hexcel Composites and designated AG-193-PW / 3501-6S. The other one was glass fibre reinforced polymer, produced by Cytec Engineering Materials and designated MXB 7701 / 7781. The first series of AG-193-PW / 3501-6S composites were produced with orientation of $0^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ$, while the remaining were with orientation of only 0° . The MXB 7701 / 7781 composites were also produced with orientation of 0° .

Table 1. The actual measurements of the composite beams

Specimens (SP)	AG-193-PW/ 3501-6S $0^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ$		AG-193-PW/ 3501-6S 0°		MXB 7701 / 7781 0°	
	SP 1	SP 2	SP 1	SP 2	SP 1	SP 2
Length (mm)	251.80	249.48	248.95	248.83	251.18	251.09
Thickness (mm)	2.75	2.77	2.58	2.56	3.46	3.44
Width (mm)	12.65	12.63	12.44	12.56	12.62	12.40
Mass (g)	13.35	13.22	11.86	11.92	19.10	18.74
Density (kg/m^3)	1524.06	1514.65	1484.34	1489.85	1741.45	1749.68

The experimental set-up

The experimental set-up is shown in Figure 2. To evaluate the flexural modulus, the beam was supported at its theoretical nodal lines, on cotton threads through U-shaped aluminium supports, at a distance $0.224l$ from each end for the fundamental mode [5]. A signal generator gave an accurate sinusoidal voltage, which was used to control a power amplifier. An electromagnetic shaker, connected to the power amplifier vibrated the beam. The response from the beam was detected via a microphone above, mid-span. The signal from the microphone was then passed through an analogue ammeter and digital multimeter. The input and output signals together connected to an oscilloscope to observe the resonant frequency.

The frequency was adjusted until the amplitude of vibration reached a maximum. The positions of the nodes were found by sprinkling dry sand on the surface of the beam. This sand migrated to the nodes where there was no displacement. Having readjusted the positions of the supports, if necessary, the natural frequency of the beam was checked again.

It is important to note that there was no contact between the shaker and the specimen during the test procedure, to measure the correct damping values of the specimens which were vibrated by means of air flow, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Experimental set-up for dynamic measurements of composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The tests were carried out under controlled environment where the temperature and relative humidity was kept at 23 C and 50%, respectively.

Validation of the Test Method

For validation of the test method, a steel beam with dimensions of 460X25X1.6 mm³ was tested and the flexural modulus of it was found to be about 210.53 GPa. This implied that the test method produced an accurate result since the value is supposed to be so [6]

Results from the Composite Specimens

Results from the AG-193-PW / 3501-6S specimens with orientations of 0°/+45°/90°/-45° are shown in Table 1. It is seen that the flexural modulus of the composite is about 60 GPa, while the damping of that is about 0.22%. The results from the same composite but with orientation of 0° are also shown in the same table. The flexural modulus and damping values for the specimens are about 53 GPa and 0.26%, respectively. The natural frequency and flexural modulus of the former samples have higher values than those of the latter ones. However, the opposite is the case for the damping values.

The specimens from glass fibre reinforced polymer, MXB 7701 / 7781, with orientation of 0°, have a flexural modulus of approximately 18 GPa and a damping value of 0.76%. The natural frequency of the these specimens is about 182 Hz (see Table 1).

Table 1. The dynamic data for the composite specimens

Specimens (SP)	AG-193-PW/ 3501-6S 0°/+45°/90°/-45°		AG-193-PW/ 3501-6S 0°		MXB 7701 / 7781 0°	
	SP 1	SP 2	SP 1	SP 2	SP 1	SP 2
Natural Freq. (Hz)	279.54	288.62	254.28	253.20	184.90	182.22
Flex. Mod. (GPa)	60.02	60.40	52.51	52.97	18.77	18.50
η, Damping (%)	0.221	0.215	0.268	0.263	0.761	0.766

In general, it was found that the specimens having high values of flexural modulus, gave lower damping values, as to be expected [3]. Although the AG-193-PW / 3501-6S specimens had the same polymer matrix, different fibre orientations were found to have important effects on dynamic properties of them.

It was shown that the test method produced reliable and repeatable results, which was proved by obtaining the correct value of flexural modulus for the steel specimen. Although there could be several specimen set-ups with different end conditions [7], such as free-clamped and

clamped-clamped, Guild and Adams [8] are critical of cantilever beam configurations claiming that in general, free-free configurations give lower and more reliable values of loss factor than cantilever arrangements and are to be preferred. Because the friction in the clamps in a cantilever is never known exactly, it can lead to substantial increases in the measured material damping if the clamping pressure is not sufficiently high.

CONCLUSIONS

The dynamic properties of composites could be found successfully by using vibrating beam technique. One of the most accurate ways of measuring the damping value of a composite beam is to use the specimen with free-free end conditions. It has been shown that the fibre orientations have important effects on the properties of composites.

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